

FORMATION OF AN INTEGRATED SYSTEM OF STATE ECONOMIC SECURITY

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Abstract: the article examines the specifics of the formation of an integrated system of economic security of the state in modern conditions. The peculiarities of the impact of risks and threats on the functioning of the economic security system are determined. The main functional elements of the integrated system of economic security have been clarified. The importance of the formation of the mechanism of economic security for the protection of the national economy of the country has been proven. The structural elements of the mechanism of economic security in modern conditions are defined. It is proposed to introduce integrated systems of economic security of the state to combine all elements of state management of the national economy into a single system.

Keywords: economic security; system of economic security; mechanism of economic security; national economy.

1 Introduction

In modern conditions, the formation of integrated systems of economic security is of particular importance, as with the help of them, it would be possible to carry out general management of the security of the national economy on the basis of differentiation or general avoidance of potential risks and threats from external factors. At the same time, in general, the effective functioning of the mechanism for ensuring the economic security of the state should be based on effective integrated system of economic security. In turn, the main element of such a system should be specific principles of implementation of the available tools for managing economic processes. At the same time, the management process itself must be implemented on the basis of effective risk management that may affect the functionality of the country's national economy. That is why such approaches to anti-crisis risk management, which contribute to ensuring the effectiveness of the functioning of integrated systems of economic security, are gaining particular relevance at present.

It should also be noted that at the current stage of development of the world economy, the riskiness of conducting economic activity increases due to the constant instability of economic processes in the countries of the world community, and insufficient information about the state of their economy. It is implied that in today's fast-moving conditions of the development of economic processes at all levels, economic activity is objectively connected with the need to make risk management decisions, which may result in an increase in the profitability of the functioning of certain industries or spheres of economic activity or may lead to significant losses in the same industries.

Therefore, the relevance of the study of practical aspects of the formation of integrated systems of economic security of the state is currently due to the significant aggravation of the problem of the national economy from the side of external factors. This is mainly due to the fact that the economic sphere is the basis for the safe functioning of all other spheres of social life. That is why the development of such an economic security strategy, which would contribute to the formation of the main directions of ensuring security and sustainable development for any state in future periods, is of particular importance.

2 Literature Review

The general toolkit and conceptual apparatus of economic security are currently at the stage of formation and categorical development. This process is multifaceted and covers all aspects of the economic security system not only in the objective and subjective dimensions, reflecting scientific creativity and influencing the evolution of scientific interests and searches of both individual scientists and collective, scientific schools. Thus,

it is worth noting the thorough research in the field of formation of the economic security of the state, revealed in the works of such scientists as O. Agres [1], I. Balaniuk [3], A. Boiar [5], M. Dziamulych [17-27], T. Shmatkovska [33-38], O. Shubalyi [40-41], O. Stashchuk [46-48], I. Yakoviyk [50], O. Yatsukh [52].

Modern studies of practical aspects of the formation of integrated systems of economic security of the state are aimed at determining the principles of applying various models of economic security management. In particular, this problem is sufficiently widely disclosed in the specialized works of such researchers as O. Apostolyuk [2], O. Binert [4], I. Britchenko [6-14], Y. Chaliuk [15], D. Kolesnikov [28], I. Revak [32], A. Shvorak [39], R. Sodoma [42-45], A. Tiurina [49], Ya. Yanyshyn [51].

At the same time, the significant changes currently taking place in the global system of economic relations contribute to the formation of a significant amount of new risks and threats to the state's economic security system, which require the creation of an effective package of anti-crisis measures aimed at avoiding or levelling them. Accordingly, there is an objective need to deepen research in the field of ensuring the effectiveness of integrated economic security systems.

3 Materials and Methods

In the economic literature, a wide arsenal of methodological approaches to the study of complex economic phenomena related to the formation of integrated systems of economic security of the state has been formed.

In particular, expert methods are used in the study of economic security to assess integral indicators of the state of development of the domestic market. Based on this, it becomes possible to assess risks and security threats to the development of the internal market. It is about a system of economic interests of subjects of economic activity and the population, which adapts to the market environment as it reaches a sufficient level of efficiency. Therefore, expert methods in many cases are able to present a higher objectivity of economic security assessment than the use of individual relative indicators based on collected statistical information [29].

Another approach to the study of the state's economic security systems is methodical methods of situational analysis. Their application assumes that economic security is a dynamic phenomenon and its assessment should be multivariate, based on the results of which it should be possible to build a model of conceptual measures to solve the problems of economic security of the state at different hierarchical levels of management. The main essence of assessment by the methods of situational analysis should be to identify areas where the probability of negative trends is high. In particular, when assessing the economic security of the state, it is important to determine the scenarios for improving the organizational and economic foundations of the internal market functioning and increasing the competitiveness of domestic producers [31].

If it is necessary to obtain accurate calculations in the process of assessing the state of economic security of the state, it is advisable to use the method of mathematical modeling. The results of this method can serve as a basic foundation for researching the state and trends in the formation of economic security systems according to any approach. In addition, mathematical modeling allows specifying expert statements regarding the functioning of integrated systems of economic security, and also contributes to the construction of an effective system of support and decision-making in the field of economic security.

Less common in studies of economic security systems of the state is the use of the optimization method, with the help of which the limit values of economic security indicators are established, on the which opportunities to assess its state are

based. The grouping of individual criteria and the determination of their limit values enables a methodical assessment of the state of economic security of the state, which acquires special importance in the case of significant discrepancies in statistical data in various spheres of economic activity.

4 Results and Discussion

The specifics of forming and ensuring the effective operation of integrated systems of economic security is the need to create appropriate tools for managing economic security at the state level. In this aspect, it should be noted that certain processes in the national economic system, which under the basic scenario are regulated by market mechanisms and do not involve external intervention, should be subject to regulatory influence. However, strengthening of the influence of political risks on the investment and production sphere, in particular, requires the state management bodies to acquire ownership rights to certain types of assets or regulate foreign investment activity in the national economy.

The purpose of such activity is to ensure the future safe operation of the relevant industries, as well as to observe the interests of the state regarding the development of the relevant spheres and branches of economic activity. Thus, it can be said that ensuring the effectiveness of integrated economic security systems depends on the comprehensive implementation of the provisions of regulatory influence on economic processes, which in practice should be expressed as specialized preventive measures applied in the event of occurrence of certain risks or threats to the national economy.

In general, the economic security of the state is a complex concept, which includes subjects, objects, and the mechanism for implementing security as a whole. At the same time, the integrated system of economic security of the state is individual one, and its functionality depends on a significant number of factors, both external and internal interaction [30]. One of the elements of the integrated system of economic security of the state is its functional components, which represent a set of main areas of economic security that differ among themselves in terms of essential characteristics. Therefore, in order to achieve the effectiveness of the integrated system of economic security of the state, it is necessary, first of all, to ensure the stability and efficiency of the functioning of all its main components. It should also be noted that each of the functional components of the integrated system of economic security of the state is characterized by its own content, a set of functional criteria, and methods of provision and implementation. In turn, the detailed list of such components may differ in different security systems depending on the specifics of their construction. However, in practice, it is possible to single out a typical set of such components of an integral system that can be included in most functional systems of the state's economic security (Table 1).

Table 1: The main functional components of the integrated system of economic security of the state

Component of the system of economic security	Essential characteristic
Financial	achieving the most efficient use of the resources of the national economy
Intellectual and personnel	preservation and development of the state's intellectual potential, effective personnel management
Technical and technological	the degree of compliance of the technologies used in the national economy with the best world analogs with the optimization of the cost of production resources
Foreign economic	the ability of the national economy to resist external threats, to adapt and realize its economic interests in the domestic and foreign markets
Energy	protection of the interests of the state as a

component	whole in the energy sector from implicit and potential threats of an internal and external nature
Political and legal	comprehensive legal support for business entities and their compliance with current legislation
Investment and innovation	ensuring active investment and innovation activity.
Ecological	compliance with current environmental standards, minimization of costs from environmental pollution
Information and communication	effective information and analytical support for the functioning of the integrated system of economic security

Source: [16].

Thus, we can see that the integrated system of economic security of the state involves preserving the economic-technological and organizational-social integrity of the national economy and overcoming risks and threats. At the same time, the appropriate level of economic security of the state in modern conditions is achieved through the implementation of a balanced state economic policy based on effective security measures, which must be adequate to the available level of existing and potential threats and risks. It can be argued that without such an economic policy, which is based on an integrated system of economic security, it is impossible to achieve a high level of efficiency in the functioning of the national economy management mechanism and to form effective mechanisms of social security and protection of the country's population.

As we can see, the conceptual goal of the process of ensuring economic security is to achieve such a state of the national economy that would create favorable conditions for the development and strengthening of the economic potential of the state in general. An important prerequisite for the effective functioning of the economic security system is the determination of strategic priorities and the observance of national interests in all spheres of the national economy.

At the same time, it is necessary to remember that the system of economic security is capable of effectively counteracting negative manifestations and destructive factors and ensuring economic security, performing informational, preventive, analytical, and prognostic functions. The information function consists in obtaining by economic security subjects complete and reliable information about the state of security objects and the probability of the occurrence of real and potential threats in order to take appropriate measures. The preventive function is associated with the use of a set of preventive measures aimed at preventing or minimizing economic losses due to the occurrence of real threats. The analytical and prognostic function is aimed at analyzing management information, identifying problems, establishing cause-and-effect relationships, patterns, and trends in the development of systemic negative phenomena, reflecting the objective situation, and developing a scientific forecast of economic development prospects [32]. Accordingly, the development of the economic security system involves its likely qualitative change and the ability to generate new qualities that are not inherent in the elements of the system, and thus acquire properties that provide a greater overall effect than the sum of the effects of the elements of the system.

The practical implementation of such functions of the economic security system is possible only through the formation of an integrated system of economic security of the state. On a practical level, the construction of such an integrated system requires the presence of a functional mechanism for ensuring and guaranteeing the economic security of the state in general. Namely on the basis of its components, an integrated system of economic security should be built since its functioning is inextricably linked both with the economic policy of the state, which must be implemented on the basis of economic security, and with the functioning of the national economy of the country, to guarantee the safe functioning of which an integrated system is created.

Therefore, it can be stated that the main place in the process of formation of the integrated system of economic security of the state is occupied by the mechanism of strengthening economic security, the structure of which is represented by methods, levers, tools, and appropriate support (Table 2).

Table 2: Structural elements of the mechanism for ensuring the economic security of the state

Structural elements of the economic security mechanism	Components of structural elements
Methods	- organizational; - economic; - special; - socio-psychological; - administrative.
Tools	- technologies; - programs.
Levers	- legal; - economic; - financial;
Software	- legal; - normative; - informative; - personnel; - financial.

Source: formed by the author.

This mechanism acts as a basic element of the integrated system of economic security of the state, with the help of which security subjects guarantee the safe condition and development of all security objects. The practical action of such a mechanism aimed at strengthening economic security requires the implementation of the following measures for the formation of the economic security system of the state itself: substantiating the strategy and tactics of strengthening economic security; selecting of the most important indicators of economic security; monitoring of factors that pose a threat to the economic security of the state; implementation of economic diagnostics; analysis of indicators of the effectiveness of measures to ensure the economic security of the state, etc.

Therefore, the mechanism for strengthening economic security is characterized by a set of effective, coordinated tools used to increase the level of economic security and, on this basis, it guarantees favorable conditions for economic and social development, increases the competitiveness of the national economy and welfare of citizens. The application of the mechanism for strengthening economic security comes down to the fact that the state tries to ensure its most complete compliance with the requirements of the macroeconomic policy of a specific period, which precedes the full implementation of its goals and objectives. Accordingly, the formation of integrated systems of economic security on the basis of this mechanism allows to significantly increase the effectiveness of their practical application.

5 Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded that the practical aspects of the formation of integrated systems of economic security of the state necessarily require the implementation of measures to coordinate the regulatory influence of state institutions on the national economy with the needs of the economic security system to avoid or differentiate potential risks and threats in accordance with the formed action plan. In turn, the formation of such plans involves the use of specialized tools and determines the need for the formation of mathematical and econometric models of economic security, which should be based on modern information technologies. The reason for this is the objective need for integrated security systems to ensure the efficiency of processing large amounts of data regarding online risks and threats. Therefore, it can be argued that an effective integrated system of economic security of the state requires effective methods of planning and analysis of risks and threats at each

level of horizontal and vertical connections between key areas of the national economy.

Improving the functioning of integrated systems of economic security should also include the formation of vertically integrated structures that will allow combining of all elements of state management of the national economy into a single, continuously operating system. Thanks to this, it will be possible to increase the transparency of the functioning of certain branches of the national economy, which will make it possible to manage the activities of its strategic sectors more effectively. By connecting separate elements of economic security into a single integrated system, the state gets the opportunity to identify existing problems to a greater extent and, accordingly, solve them more effectively. Therefore, the formation of an integrated system of economic security of the state provides opportunities for strengthening the security of the national economy, stabilizing its individual problem areas and increasing the economic security of the state in general.

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Primary Paper Section: A

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